

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TEIH****FIRST NAME: BELINDA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic Writing (EUCLID 2024, 11)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
3. American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 25)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 41)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) has always been one of my goals in my academic journey. However, the expectations of achieving this goal have always been scary until I had the courage to enroll in the program this year. The scariest part of this was when I received the orientation email and logged into the LMS portal. My first glance at the course pack kept me wondering if I would meet the expectations of the program since I have been out of school for a while and my mixed language background (French and English) since my country of origin had two colonial masters though I have always assumed that my English language is perfect. However, after going through the course pack and receiving an assuring email from the course instructor, I am regaining my confidence and braising up to learn all the good writing habits expected from me to be successful in the program and to unlearn all the bad writing habits I have learned through my years in school.

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru and the video presentation by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck have made me realize that I still have a lot of learning and unlearning to do as far as formal or professional

academic writing is concerned. Before now, I had not mastered the differences between American and British English and did not even know that it matters in academic writing.

This response paper will focus on the major concepts learned from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period one and the tutorial videos. These concepts are academic essay writing, punctuation, American and British English, plagiarism and style guide

2) ACADEMIC WRITING

Chapter one of the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one course pack focuses on the importance and types of academic essays. Throughout this chapter, emphasis is laid on the rules and purpose of academic essays which is to “communicate ideas based on evidence” (EUCLID 2024, 7). Although writing an academic essay does not follow a linear path, there are guidelines for writing a good one. These are:

- Early start-up
- Defining the question and analyzing the task
- Drafting the initial plan

Good academic writing is backed by evidence that can be obtained from research. Research helps the writer to learn more about the topic by understanding complex issues and addressing them effectively. Creative and critical thinking are also important aspects of good academic writing. According to Cleenwerck and Gulma, “creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas and try techniques like brainstorming or mind wrapping while critical thinking narrows the focus or scope of your ideas” (EUCLID 2024, 11).

Writing and editing the essay are also some very important aspects of academic essay writing, if not all the research and planning will be in vain; and of course, the essay writing process is not finished until it is submitted.

a) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation signs and the correct use of these signs give more meaning to academic essays. The ACA-401/ACA-401D period one (1) course pack is very elaborate on punctuation marks, how and where to use them to give sentences their real meaning. Some of these punctuation signs are:

- Apostrophe
- Brackets
- Colon and semicolon
- Comma
- Dashes and hyphens
- Full stop
- exclamation mark

- Question mark
- Quotation mark

b) AMERICAN AND BRITISH STYLE

The aspect of differentiating between American and British English in writing academic essays is very new to me and important to know. Coming from a French-speaking dominating country due to its colonization history and having done part of my studies in the United States, I am always caught up between French, British, and American English when writing my academic papers. Reading through the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one (1) course pack, I have known better to always focus on a particular language, though the difference is more on pronunciation and spellings than on the meaning of words, “they are more similar than different especially with educated or scientific English” (EUCLID 2024, 25), it is however imperative to master the difference when it comes to academic writing.

i) PLAGIARISM

This is a very serious crime in academic writing. According to ACA-401/ACA-401D period one course pack, “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author” (EUCLID 2024, 34). Whether this unauthorized use of information is done consciously or unconsciously, it is prohibited and punishable by the law. However, using information or phrases from other writers is a very important aspect of academic writing and credit should always be given to other information sources to avoid plagiarism. This can be done by “properly citing the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2024, 34). In-text citations, paraphrasing and quotations are all measures of preventing plagiarism and giving credit to the authors. Acknowledging the source of any information used in writing academic essays is very important and constitutes the ethics of good writing.

ii) STYLE GUIDE

This section of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack highlights a set of rules and standards to ensure a perfect flow in language, formatting and tone in academic writing. According to ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period one, style guide is defined as “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2024, 41). Whichever writing style is chosen, consistency is the key and “EUCLID recommends the Chicago rules (Turabian) (EUCLID 2024, 41). Without style in writing, the finished academic essay won’t make sense. Emphasis has been laid on some elements of style like:

- Preferred sentence length
- Manuscript layout
- Font usage
- Spelling

- Use of abbreviations
- Accepted terminology
- The use of symbols
- Voice of preference
- Structure
- Paragraph numbering and indention
- The use of headings

Style Guide portrays some professionalism in academic essays and makes them easy to read and understand, and it is very important for PhD students to familiarize themselves with. This course pack elaborates details the Chicago style, “which is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual” (EUCLID 2024,44), and the Turabian style, which is “... the Chicago style applied to research paper” (EUCLID 2024, 44).

3) CONCLUSION

As the saying goes, “a stitch in time saves nine” (unknown). This is exactly what I felt after reading through ACA-401/ACA-401D period one course pack. The proper mastery of the entire course means laying a solid foundation for the PhD program that is all about research and writing. Just when I thought I am a good writer, the introductory phase of this course has made me to understand that I still have a lot of learning and unlearning to do as far as English language and academic writing is concern. However, I still have the impression that academic writing is very complex. Rigid and time consuming. It is too formal for my liking but then it differentiates scholars from street writers. As it is often said, “nothing good comes easy” being a good researcher, and professional academic writer means a lot of commitment to learning and I am bracing myself for the task of becoming a PhD holder.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.